

**AVI-FAUNAL DIVERSITY AND THEIR PATHOLOGICAL EFFECT ON
PLANTS IN THE NIGERIAN ARMY UNIVERSITY BIU CAMPUS, BIU
LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA OF BORNO STATE, NIGERIA**

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ABSTRACT: Avifaunal diversity in the Biu campus of the Nigerian Army University has caused major pathological effects on Plant health. This has been greatly due to land-use changes and plant-bird interactions. This bird species diversity can affect interactions between birds and plants and a host of other characteristics in various habitats. Therefore, this research aims to determine the diversity of bird species and the methods by which plant diseases are spread by birds in the Biu campus of the Nigerian Army University. Data collection was carried out from June 2024, to late May 2025, encompassing the wet and dry seasons. The experiment was completely randomized with three replicates. Data were analyzed using the statistical package for social sciences (SPSS) version 23.0. Forty-four (44) bird's species were identified in the campus, which were categorized under ten (10) orders and twenty six (26) families during both the wet and dry seasons. The order Passeriformes had a high number of species of birds (29 %), followed by Ciconiiformes (27 %). Abyssinian white-eye (*Zosterops abyssinicus*), African citril (*Citragra citrinelloides*) and baglafaecht weaver (*Ploceus baglafaecht*) were found to transmit both bacterial and fungal diseases. Eleven (11) plant diseases were identified as being spread by certain bird species. Some of the plant diseases were caused by multiple bird species through feeding, bird droppings, and nesting methods.

Keywords: Avi-fauna, Diversity, Pathological, Effects, Healthy, Plants

INTRODUCTION

The exploration of avian species diversity and distribution patterns is vital parts of conservation efforts in biodiversity-rich environments such as the Nigerian Army University Biu campus. Compared with other species, birds are relatively well-known and easily observed, making them great markers of productivity or biodiversity (Keesing et al, 2010). Fruit and grain-eating birds may aid in the dispersal of diseases in green spaces (Abharna and Dattu, 2015). Intriguingly, avifauna diversity may play a dual role in the emergence and transmission of infectious diseases (Pullanikkatil and Chilambo, 2010). On the one hand, high bird diversity may provide a

larger potential source of novel pathogens, but on the other hand, bird diversity can reduce further pathogen transmission for both long-established and newly emerging diseases (Desalegn and Abebe, 2024). Loss of avifauna diversity might affect disease transmission through several mechanisms. If each species effect on pathogen transmission were entirely idiosyncratic (Abharna and Dattu, 2015), one would expect that declines in diversity would be equally likely to cause a decrease or an increase in disease transmission in the remaining species (Yasin and Tekalign, 2022). However, in recent years, a consistent picture has emerged, biodiversity loss tends to increase pathogen transmission and disease incidence. This pattern occurs across ecological systems that vary in pathogen type, host, ecosystem, and transmission mode (Keesing et al, 2010).

Diversity has a similar effect on plant diseases, with species losses increasing the transmission of two fungal rust pathogens that infect perennial rye grass and other plant species (Pullanikkatil and Chilambo, 2010). For plants, seeding experimental fields with plant species that are not hosts for fungal pathogens decreased the pathogen load of species that are hosts, by threefold, apparently by reducing host density through competition (Desalegn and Abebe, 2024). However, a greater diversity of host species can sometimes increase pathogen transmission by increasing the abundance of vectors (Yasin and Tekalign, 2022). Multiple mechanisms operate in concert for some disease systems (Pullanikkatil and Chilambo, 2010), leading to a compounding effect of bird diversity loss on increased disease transmission. Recent research has focused on assessing the mechanisms by which reduced biodiversity increases pathogen transmission (Desalegn and Abebe, 2024).

The establishment of Nigerian Army University Biu as the first 'prospective' green University in Africa by the combining of small villages, farmlands, and mountain landscapes into a single institution ought, to live up to its budding reputation and purpose of establishment as an institution of learning as well as a biodiversity, conservation, and research center. However, there is a need for sustainable practice through purposeful efforts toward upholding crucial habitats for bird diversity on the campuses. Habitat loss or conversion to human-occupied structures is associated with urbanization and is considered a major threat to species survival (Keesing et al., 2010). The species variety and distribution of the local avian fauna, particularly in NAUB and the surrounding farmlands, has received little or no attention. The study gathered baseline information for the university on bird species diversity and the pathological effect of birds-plants interactions. Although there are many reports on the assessment of Avi-faunal diversity in different parts of the globe, none have focused on bird species diversity and their pathological effect on healthy plants.

MATERIALS AND METHOD

Study Area

This study was conducted in the Biu Local Government Area, within the campus of the Nigerian Army University Biu, Borno State, Nigeria. The LGA is located in the southern part of Borno State, about 210 kilometers from Maiduguri, the state capital. It is located between Latitudes 10.25°N to 11.00°N and Longitudes 11.42°E to 12.30°E with a population of approximately 175,760 in 2006 and a projected population of 839,460 persons in 2018 at a 3.4 % growth rate, (National Population Commission, 2006). It lies on the Biu Plateau at an average elevation of 626 m above sea level and is located in the agro-ecological zone of Northern Guinea savannah with a small portion in the northeast. The study area is bordered by the Damboa, Chibok, and Askira-Uba LGAs of the State to the north and the Bayo, Kwaya-Kusar, and Shani LGAs to the south (Encyclopedia Britannica, 2009). The average temperature in Biu Local Government is 23.7 °C and about 888-mm of

precipitation falls annually. There are two cropping seasons, one that starts with early onset of rain, usually in May and the other that starts soon after harvesting of the rain-fed crops between November and December (Encyclopedia Britannica, 2009). Agriculture is the main activity in the area. The economy is mixed agriculture based on herding cattle, goats, sheep, horses, and donkeys and arable farming of sorghum, millet, maize, cowpea, and cotton. The study was conducted within the university campus (Figure 1). The campus is a typical sprawling urban environment characterized by old and new buildings, emerging road networks, newly established avenue tree plantations, remnant native flora, exotic ornamental plants species, and synanthropic bird species. It occupies a very large land area of which over 75 % is yet to be developed and currently serves as an agricultural area for subsistence farming. It has a gallery forest with a perennial and seasonal stream that hosts some water-dependent bird species and other associated taxa. The study area includes *Mangifera indica*, *Ensete ventricosum*, *Eucalyptus camaldulensis*, *Eucalyptus globulus*, *Ficus sycomorus*, *Grevillea robusta*, *Pinus* spp., *Juniperus procera*, *Acacia senegalensis*, and *Vernonia amygdalina*. Common crop types include vegetables, beans, rice, millet, maize, soybeans, and groundnuts.

Figure 1: Map of Biu Local Government Area Showing the Study Area (NAUB)

Source: Digitized in the GIS Laboratory, Department of Geography, NAUB (2025).

Data Collection and Sampling Design: To gather reliable data, the researchers used a geospatial positioning system (GPS 72hz to determine the location of the sampling area, field binoculars to determine the clear vision

of bird species at a distance, a notebook to register a list of birds before entering to SPSS and pen to write the checklist of birds), and bird guidebook was used during the study period.

Data collection was carried out from June 2024, to late May 2025, encompassing the wet and dry seasons. The dry season covers from November to May, and the wet season is from June to October. We stratified the study area into two habitat types: farmland and settlement areas to assess the diversity of birds because the study area was not uniform in terms of habitat condition. The sampling unit within the habitat was determined and assigned based on the area coverage. The line transect technique and total count were employed to assess the diversity of bird species in the two habitats.

A total of 21 sampling line transects were generated systematically using ArcGIS 10.8.1. Of these, 16 line transects were employed on the farmland and 5 were at the settlement. The transect length was 1.2 km in both farmland and settlement habitats. The distance between each sampling transect was 250 m to avoid double counting of avian species. Bird species were observed by moving along the transect using naked eyes, field binoculars, and a guidebook for better identification. The transects were simultaneously covered data collectors and were adjusted for each transect. The data collectors used the following features: external morphology (shape, color, size, beak leg, and tail), song, call, plumage patterns, and habitat type. Data were collected in early morning in 6:30 to 10:00 and late afternoon from 15:30 to 18.00 when birds were more active and on days with good weather conditions. A waiting period of 3 to 5 minutes before counting was applied to minimize disturbance during count. A total of 32 surveys were conducted in each of the census sites, covering 16 in the wet and 16 in the dry seasons. The observation trial was conducted once per week and four times per month. Observed species were noted and recorded on the prepared data sheet. To obtain accurate data, well-experienced researchers and bird experts were involved during the study period. The relative abundance of avian species was determined using the following equation: $RA (\%) = n/N * 100$ where n is the number of individuals of a particular species recorded and N is the total number of individuals of the species.

Experimental Equipment

The equipment used in the experiment included camera, field binoculars, a guidebook, a GPS meter, a notebook to register a list of birds, a pen to write the checklist of birds, an autoclave, a knife, a binocular microscope, a microscopic slide, a sliding cover, a conical flask, a 250 ml and a 500 ml beaker, an inoculating loop, a cotton wool, a cork-borer, a foil, a Bunsen burner, Petri-dishes and a masking tape. The reagents used include Distillate water, ethanol, lactophenol, potato dextrox agar (PDA), and nutrient agar.

Sterilization of the Materials

The Petri dishes used for culturing were sterilized. The inoculating needle and the cork borer were also sterilized by flaming over a Bunsen burner and allowed to cool by dipping them in methanol. The prepared media was autoclaved for 15 min at 10 lbs pressure at 121 °C and allowed to cool. The organisms were inoculated in a sterilised environment in the inoculation chamber. The table in the inoculation chamber was wiped with 95 % alcohol, and the glasswares was exposed to ultraviolet light (UV light) for 30 min. before inoculation.

Preparation of Culture Media and Inoculum Plating

Potato dextrose agar (PDA) and nutrient agar were used for culturing fungal and bacterial isolates, respectively. Thirty-nine grams (39 g) of PDA and nutrient agar were dissolved in 1 L of distilled water. The solutions were

poured into a conical flask, and 6 ml (0.1%) of streptomycin was added to the sterilized PDA media, just before pouring into Petri dishes, to prevent bacterial growth, while the Nutrient Agar was not. The mouth of the conical flask was plugged and covered with cotton, and wrapped with aluminum foil before autoclaving at 121° C for 15 min at 10 lbs. Pressure. The media was poured into the Petri dishes in the inoculation chamber. Twenty (20) ml of the media was poured into 9-cm diameter Petri dishes in three replicates and, allowed to cool and solidify under ultraviolet light.

Determination of Fungi and Bacterial Pathogens in Plant Samples

Samples of plant parts (leaves, flowers, stems, seeds, twigs etc.) on which the birds feed or used in making their nests were collected from various feeding and nesting sites to identify the disease pathogen transmitted by various birds species on plants within the NAUB campus. , These samples were brought straight to the laboratory where they were sliced into 5 mm square sections each and sterilized in 0.1 % mercuric chloride solution for 30 seconds in sterilized Petri dishes. These were then rinsed in three to five changes of sterile distilled water to remove the sterilant. The sliced portions were then blotted dry using sterile filter papers and transferred into the solidified PDA and NA plates using sterilized forceps. They were placed at the center of the Petri dishes and incubated at room temperature (30 ±3 °C) in the laboratory for 7 days for fungal growth and 48 h for bacterial growth. After incubation, the presence (+) or absence (-) of fungal or bacterial pathogens against the bird species were recorded.

Preparation of slides and identification of fungi and bacteria

Microscopic examination was performed to observe the structure and characteristics of the fungal and bacterial isolates. A sterile needle was used to pick a small portion from the pure cultures which were then placed on a sterile glass slide stained with Lactophenol in cotton blue and examined under a microscope. Micrographs of the isolates showing their microstructures were taken. The observed morphological and structural characteristics were compared with the structures in the Hunter and Barnett identification guides.

Data Analysis: Data were summarized by seasons per habitat type during the study period in the Excel spreadsheet. SPSS version 23.0 statistical package software was used for the statistical analysis, and PAST (Paleontological Statistics) software, version 3.26, was used to calculate Shannon–Wiener diversity (H') and evenness (J/E). The square root transformation revealed that the data were not uniformly distributed. For non-normally distribution data, Mann–Whitney and Kruskal–Wallis statistical tests are appropriate. The effect of seasons on species abundance was analyzed using the Mann–Whitney test, and Kruskal–Wallis statistical tests were also used to analyze bird abundance between habitats.

RESULTS

The 44 bird species identified on the Nigerian Army University Biu campus were, categorized under ten (10) orders and twenty six (26) families during both the wet and dry seasons. The order Passeriformes has a high number species of birds (29 %), followed by Ciconiiformes (27 %) (Figure 2). The order Apodiformes, Galliformes, and Strigiformes contain one family each. Among the 44 identified bird species, the Speckled Pigeon (*Columba guinea*), White-Collar Pigeon (*Columba albitorques*), and Red-Eye Dove (*Streptopelia semitorquata*) are residential or endemic to NAUB, whereas the Black Stork (*Ciconia nigra*), Secretary Bird (*Sagittarius serpentarius*), and Great Heron (*Ardea goliath*) are all migratory birds. Based on the IUCN Red List category status, the Mountain White-Eye (*Zosterops japonicus*) is critically endangered while Ruppell's Robin-

Chat (*Cossypha semirufa*) and Mountain Thrush (*Turdus plebejus*) are near extinction. The Secretary Bird (*Sagittarius serpentarius*) and the Black Stork (*Ciconia nigra*) are vulnerable. However, the remaining majority of the bird species are categorized under least concern (Table 1).

Table 1. Avian Diversity and Migratory/Residential and IUCN Status

Order of the species	Family	Common name	Scientific name	M/R	IUCN status
Accipitriformes	Accipitridae	Yellow-Billed Kite	<i>Milvus aegyptius</i>	M	LC
		Augur Buzzard	<i>Buteo augur</i>	R	LC
		Black Kite	<i>Milvus migrans</i>	M	LC
		Hawk	<i>Accipiter gentilis</i>	R	LC, NT, and VU
	Sagittaridae	Swallow-Tailed Kite	<i>Elanoides forficatus</i>	M	LC
Secretary Bird		<i>Sagittarius serpentarius</i>	M	VU	
Apodiformes	Apodidae	Common Swift	<i>Apus apus</i>	M	LC
Coliiformes	Coliidae	Speckled Mouse-Bird	<i>Colius striatus</i>	R	LC
Columbiformes	Columbidae	Speckled Pigeon	<i>Columba guinea</i>	R	LC
		White-Collar Pigeon	<i>Columba albitorques</i>	R	LC
		Red-Eye Dove	<i>Streptopelia semitorquata</i>	R	LC
		Ring-Neck Dove	<i>Streptopelia capicola</i>	R	LC
		Dusky turtle dove	<i>Streptopelia lugens</i>	R	LC
		Rock pigeon	<i>Columba livia</i>	R	LC
Coraciiformes	Meropidae	Little Bee-Eater	<i>Merops pusillus</i>	R	LC
	Alcedinidae	Kingfisher	<i>Alcedo atthis</i>	R	LC
Ciconiiformes	Ciconiidae	Black Stork	<i>Ciconia nigra</i>	M	VU
Passeriformes	Corvidae	Pied Crow	<i>Corvus albus</i>	R	LC
		Fan-Tailed Raven	<i>Corvus rhipidurus</i>	R	LC
		Common Bulbul	<i>Pycnonotus barbatus</i>	R	LC
	Pycnonotidae	Moorland Chat	<i>Pinarochroa sordida</i>	R	LC
	Muscicapidae	Ruppell's Robin-Chat	<i>Cossypha semirufa</i>	R	EX
	Turdidae	Mountain Thrush	<i>Turdus plebejus</i>	M	EX
	Passeridae	Swainson's Sparrow	<i>Passer swainsonii</i>	M	LC

		Groundscraper Thrush	Turdus litsitsirupa	R	LC
	Ploceidae	Baglafaecht Weaver	Ploceus baglafaecht	R	LC
		Little Weaver	Ploceus luteolus	R	LC
		Village Weaver	Ploceus cucullatus	R	LC
		Red-Cheeked Cordon-Bleu	Uraeginthus bengalus	R	LC
	Estrildidae	Red-Billed Firefinch	Lagonosticta senegala	R	LC
		Mountain White-Eye	Zosterops japonicus	R	CE
	Zosteropidae	Abyssinian White-Eye	Zosterops abyssinicus	R	LC
	Nectariniidae	Scarlet-Chested Sunbird	Chalcomitra senegalensis	R	LC
		African Citril	Citragra citrinelloides	R	LC
		Brown-Rumped Seedeater	Serinus tristriatus	R	LC
	Viduidae	Village Indigobird	Vidua chalybeate	R	LC
	Sturnidae	Greater Blue-eared Starling (BES)	Lamprotornis chalybaeus	R	LC
		The African Paradise Flycatcher	Terpsiphone viridis	R	LC
	Motacillidae	White Wagtail	Motacilla alba	M, R	LC
	Threskiornithidae	African Sacred Ibis	Threskiornis aethiopicus	M, R	LC
		Cattle Egret	Bubulcus ibis	M, R	LC
	Ardeidae	Great Heron	Ardea goliath	M	LC
Galliformes	Phasianidae	Erckel's Francolin	Pternistis erckelii	R	LC
Strigiformes	Tytonidae	Owl	Bubo africanus	R	LC

NB.: R residential; M migratory; LC least concern; NT near threatened; VU vulnerable; CE critically endangered; EX near-to-extinction

Figure 2: Pi-Chat showing the percentage distribution of the order of birds in the study area

Table 2 shows the feeding habits of the 44 identified bird species, the type of plant diseases (bacterial or fungal), and the mode of transmission of these diseases. Birds were categorized on the basis of their feeding habits. The foraging guild of the birds overlapped, resulting in two or more birds falling under the same foraging category. The African Paradise Flycatcher (*Terpsiphone viridis*), and Little Bee-Eater (*Merops pusillus*) are typically insectivorous, and most bird species have similar feeding habits.

Most of the birds that spread fungal pathogens on plants also transmit bacterial diseases either on the same plant or a different plant by feeding or nesting on the plants. Examples include the Abyssinian White-Eye (*Zosterops abyssinicus*), African Citril (*Cithegra citrinelloides*), and Baglafaecht Weaver (*Ploceus baglafaecht*). However, the African Paradise Flycatcher (*Terpsiphone viridis*), African Sacred Ibis (*Threskiornis aethiopicus*), Augur Buzzard (*Buteo augur*), and Black Kite (*Milvus migrans*) did not transmit either bacterial or fungal pathogens.

Table 2: Avian Feeding Habits, Plant Disease Causes and Modes of Transmission

No.	Common name	Scientific name	Feeding habits	Bacterial Diseases	Fungal Diseases	Mode of transmission
1.	Abyssinian White-Eye	<i>Zosterops abyssinicus</i>	I, F, and N	+	+	F, N
2.	African Citril	<i>Cithegra citrinelloides</i>	S, I, F, L	+	+	F, N
3.	The African Paradise Flycatcher	<i>Terpsiphone viridis</i>	I,	-	-	-
4.	African Sacred Ibis	<i>Threskiornis aethiopicus</i>	IN, I	-	-	-
5.	Augur Buzzard	<i>Buteo augur</i>	I, C	-	-	-
6.	Baglafaecht Weaver	<i>Ploceus baglafaecht</i>	I, S, F, and N	+	+	F, N
7.	Black Kite	<i>Milvus migrans</i>	I, C	-	-	-
8.	Black Stork	<i>Ciconia nigra</i>	I, SV, IN,	+	+	N

9.	Brown-Rumped Seedeater	<i>Serinus tristriatus</i>	G, S	+	+	F, N
10.	Cattle Egret	<i>Bubulcus ibis</i>	I, F, L	+	+	F, N
11.	Common Bulbul	<i>Pycnonotus barbatus</i>	I, SV, S, F, L	+	+	F, N
12.	Common Swift	<i>Apus apus</i>	I, F	+	-	N
13.	Dusky turtle dove	<i>Streptopelia lugens</i>	S, L	+	-	F
14.	Erckel's Francolin	<i>Pternistis erckelii</i>	I, F, S, and SH	+	+	F, N
15.	Fan-Tailed Raven	<i>Corvus rhipidurus</i>	I, F, S, and IN	+	+	F, N
16.	Great Heron	<i>Ardea goliath</i>	I, SN, SV, and IN	+	-	N
17.	Greater Blue-eared Starling (BES)	<i>Lamprotornis chalybaeus</i>	G, S, F, I	+	+	F, N
18.	Groundscraper Thrush	<i>Turdus litsitsirupa</i>	I, G	+	+	F, N
19.	Hawk	<i>Accipiter gentilis</i>	SM, IN	+	+	N
20.	Kingfisher	<i>Alcedo atthis</i>	I, SF	+	-	N
21.	Little Bee-Eater	<i>Merops pusillus</i>	I,	-	+	N
22.	Little Weaver	<i>Ploceus luteolus</i>	S, I, L	+	+	F, N
23.	Moorland Chat	<i>Pinarochroa sordida</i>	G, I	+	+	F, N
24.	Mountain Thrush	<i>Turdus plebejus</i>	G, I, and SV	+	+	F, N
25.	Mountain White-Eye	<i>Zosterops japonicus</i>	I, F, N, L	+	+	F, N
26.	Owl	<i>Bubo africanus</i>	I, SM, and IN	+	+	N
27.	Pied Crow	<i>Corvus albus</i>	I, F, S, and SV	+	+	F, N
28.	Red-Billed Firefinch	<i>Lagonosticta senegala</i>	I, S, G, and L	+	+	F, N
29.	Red-Cheeked Cordon-Bleu	<i>Uraeginthus bengalus</i>	I, S	+	+	F, N
30.	Red-Eyed Dove	<i>Streptopelia semitorquata</i>	I, S, and G	+	+	F, N
31.	Ring-Necked Dove	<i>Streptopelia capicola</i>	I, S, F, and G	+	+	F, N
32.	Rock pigeon	<i>Columba livia</i>	I, S, and G	+	+	F, N
33.	Ruppell's Robin-Chat	<i>Cossypha semirufa</i>	I, F	+	+	N
34.	Scarlet-Chested Sunbird	<i>Chalcomitra senegalensis</i>	I, N	+	+	F, N
35.	Secretary Bird	<i>Sagittarius serpentarius</i>	I, S, and V	-	+	N
36.	Speckled Mouse-Bird	<i>Colius striatus</i>	I, F, L, S, and N	+	+	F, N
37.	Speckled Pigeon	<i>Columba guinea</i>	I, S, F	+	+	F, N

38.	Swainson's Sparrow	<i>Passer swainsonii</i>	I, S, F, and G	+	+	F, N
39.	Swallow-Tailed Kite	<i>Elanoides forficatus</i>	I, SV, and IN	-	+	N
40.	Village Indigobird	<i>Vidua chalybeata</i>	I, S,	+	+	F, N
41.	Village Weaver	<i>Ploceus cucullatus</i>	S, F, I	+	+	F, N
42.	White Wagtail	<i>Motacilla alba</i>	I, IN	+	-	N
43.	White-Collared Pigeon	<i>Columba albitorques</i>	S, SH, F, and IN	+	+	F, N
44.	Yellow-Billed Kite	<i>Milvus aegyptius</i>	I, IN	-	+	N

Food habits: I, insectivorous; S, seed feeders; F, fruit feeders; L, leaves feeders; IN, invertebrates; SV, small vertebrates; SH, shoot feeders; N, nectar feeders; C, carnivorous; G, grass feeders; SF, small fishes; SM, small mammals

Mode of transmission: F, by feeding; N, by nesting

+: Presence of bacterial fungal infection

-: Absence of bacterial/fungal infection

Table 3 shows the various plant diseases and the bird species involved in their spread as observed in the Campus of Nigerian Army University Bui. Eleven (11) plant diseases were identified which include; Cryptococcus's, Dieback Disease, Cercospora leaf spot, leaf and stem rot, rice blast, rice bacterial blight, bacterial blight of soybeans, powdery mildew, verticillium wilt and leaf curl diseases were identified, - each caused by certain bird species, although some of the plant diseases were caused by multiple bird species through their feeding modes, bird droppings, and nesting methods. Birds do not directly cause plant diseases; they can only act as vectors, transmitting pathogens that cause various plant diseases. Birds can carry diseases through their droppings or by feeding on plants, which can cause soil and plants contamination. They can also spread diseases through contact with infected plants or animals.

Table 3: Birds species associated with the spread of major plant diseases in the Campus of Nigerian Army University Bui

S/No	Type of disease	Description	Birds Involved
1.	Cryptococcosis	This is a fungal disease found in bird droppings, it infects plant tissues and soils, rendering the leaves of plants reddish or dead.	Speckled pigeon, red-eyed dove, ring-necked dove, rock pigeon, and cattle egret
2.	Die-back Disease	This is a fungal or bacterial plant disease that is spread by birds while feeding on plants, especially plant shoots. The young plant or stem begins to die off from the tip of the shoot because of the spread of bacteria and fungi by the bird.	Erckel's francolin, White-collared pigeon, Greater blue-eared starling
3.	Cercospora leaf spot	It is a fungal disease that appears as tiny spots on the leaves of plants especially cultivated crops on farmlands, such as cowpea. The disease is caused by fungi that are spread by birds during feeding or	Abyssinian white-eye, african citril, baglafaecht weaver, brown-rumped seedeater

		collecting plant parts for nesting.	
4.	Fruit rot disease	Fungal and bacterial diseases that occur on fruits such as mango, guava, banana, black currant, and oranges. As a result of birds feeding or pecking on them. These birds expose, the fruit to the actions of bacterial and fungal pathogens. Fruit rot can be hard, dry, watery, slimy, or spongy.	Speckled mouse-bird, Speckled pigeon, Swainson's sparrow, Village weaver, White-collared pigeon, Ruppell's robin-chat
5.	Leaf and stem rot	This is also caused by birds that spread the fungal and bacterial pathogens by feeding or pecking on the leaves and stems of plants, thereby causing injuries that allow the pathogens to enter the tissues of the plants. Leaf and stem rot can also be hard, dry, watery, slimy or spongy.	African Citril, Cattle Egret, Common Bulbul, Dusky Turtle Dove, Little Weaver, Mountain White-Eye (MWE)
6.	Rice blast	This is a fungal disease that was observed in rice farms within the NAUB campus. It is indirectly caused by birds plucking rice leaves to make their nest, thereby exposing the wounded parts to the fungal spores of the disease. The rice blast appears as a dotted black or brown spot on the rice leaf, which reduces the yield of rice.	Little weaver, Mountain white-eye, Red-billed firefinch, Brown-rumped Seedeater, Greater blue-eared starling, and Moorland chat
7.	Rice bacterial blight	This is a deadly bacterial disease that is observed in cultivated rice fields on campus. It appears as water-soaked streaks from the leaf tips and margins that become larger and release a milky oz that dries into yellow droplets. This disease is spread by certain bird species and can reduce the yield of rice produce by 50-65%.	Brown-rumped seedeater, mountain thrush, swainson's sparrow, and red-billed firefinch
8.	Bacterial blight in soybeans	Bacterial Blight of Soybeans is also caused by bacterial pathogen (<i>pseudomonas syringea</i> pv <i>Glycine</i>) in fields where soybean is being cultivated. It appears as larger water-soaked streaks from the leaf tips and margins releasing a milky oz that dries into yellow patches. The disease is spread by certain bird species, which can significantly reduce soybean yield.	Swainson's sparrow, Red-eyed dove, red-billed firefinch, moorland chat, and Mountain white-eye
9.	Powdery mildew	Plant disease caused by many specialized races of fungal species. It occurs on different species of	Abyssinian white-eye, cattle egret, fan-tailed

		trees, shrubs, flowers, fruits, field crops, etc. Different bird species help in spreading the powdery mildew disease from one plant to another using their feathers, claws, and beaks. The disease has a white powdery appearance due to a large number of microscopic spores. It causes stunted growth of infected plants, yellowing and withering of flowers, and reduced fruit quality and yield.	raven, kingfisher, mountain white-eye, and red-eyed dove
10.	Verticillium wilt	It is a very destructive fungal disease that affects many species of trees, shrubs, flowers, fruits, and field crops. It turns the leaves on branches into dull green to yellow, wilts and withers, mostly from the base upward. The fungal agent <i>Verticillium albo-atrum</i> which is spread by some birds can cause stunted growth and fruits and plants death.	White-collared pigeon, ruppell's robin-chat, moorland chat, dusky turtle dove, and African citril
11.	Leaf curl disease	Leaf curl disease is a widespread disease that affects most plants within the campus. It is caused by environmental factors, such as climate or temperatures, and some bacterial and fungal pathogens. Examples of plants with leaf curl disease include, mango, oranges, guava, and black currant trees.	African citril, speckled mouse-bird, red-billed firefinch, mountain white-eye, little weaver, and cattle egret

DISCUSSION

The 44 bird species identified in the campus of the Nigerian Army University Biu were, categorized under ten (10) orders and twenty six (26) families during both the wet and dry seasons. The order Passeriformes has a high number of species of birds (29%) followed by Ciconiiformes (27 %) (Figure 2). The order Apodiformes, Galliformes, and Strigiformes contain one family each. There is high avian diversity in campus of the Nigerian Army University Biu this is partly due to large forest, including orchards and botanical gardens which possesses different types of vegetation that provide different ecological attributes for nesting and perching. Eveso, et al., (2022) in their studies reported seventy (71) bird species in thirty-two (32) families, similarly fifty (50) species and twenty-eight (28) families was recorded by Adam et al., (2019) in the Bade catchment area of river Yobe. Derebe et al., (2023) also reported that the order of Passeriformes has the highest number of recorded species and populations. Shiferaw and Yazezew (2020) conducted a similar survey that the order of Passeriformes has the highest number of species recorded at Ansas Dam and surrounding farmland site in, Debre Berhan Town, Ethiopia. A total of 50 bird species belonging to 28 families and 10 orders were recorded. The order Passeriformes (67.3%) had the highest number of species. The composition of bird communities differs among habitat types (Yasin and Tekalign, 2022).

The 44 identified bird species were categorized based on their feeding habits. The foraging guild of the birds overlapped, resulting in two or more birds falling under the same foraging category. However, most bird species

are predominantly insectivorous and granivorous. Seasonal variations in food sources where farmers plow farmland and annual crop species bloom during the wet and rainy seasons could be the reason for the relatively higher density of granivore feeding guild. The African Paradise Flycatcher (*Terpsiphone viridis*) and Little Bee-Eater (*Merops pusillus*) are typically insectivorous, and most bird species have similar feeding habits. This might be due to this feeding guild being the best adapter of to the human-modified agricultural area. The ability of insectivorous birds to disperse through deforested countryside helps them persist in small fragments habitat. In a similar report by Yasin and Tekalign (2022), the insectivore was the dominant feeding guild. As stated by De Bonilla et al. (2012), small landscape fragments are potential key refuges for the most diverse and specialized feeding guilds, such as granivores and insectivores. According to Muñoz-Sáez et al. (2020), a high abundance of granivores bird species in the Hg and Lf habitats might be partly associated with diverse seed-producing annual crop species that provided various food types for these birds. This finding is similar to that of Waltert et al. (2005), who showed that granivorous birds had the highest number of species in annual cultures and were significantly less species-riches in other habitat types.

Most birds spread both fungal and bacterial pathogens on the same and a different plant by feeding or nesting on the plants. Examples include the Abyssinian White-Eye (*Zosterops abyssinicus*), African Citril (*Citroica citrinelloides*), and Baglafaecht Weaver (*Ploceus baglafaecht*). This is because birds can fly from one place to another, and in the process, they come in contact with pathogen spores that they carry via their feathers, beak, hoofs, or droppings, which they transmit to healthy plants when feeding, nesting, or roosting. However, the African Paradise Flycatcher (*Terpsiphone viridis*), African Sacred Ibis (*Threskiornis aethiopicus*), Augur Buzzard (*Buteo augur*), and Black Kite (*Milvus migrans*) did not transmit either bacterial or fungal pathogens. Eleven (11) plant diseases were identified during the studies, including;- Cryptococcosis, Dieback Disease, Cercospora leaf spot, leaf and stem rot, rice blast, rice bacterial blight, bacterial blight of soybeans, powdery mildew, verticillium wilt and leaf curl diseases, and the bird species involved in spreading them, as observed in the Nigerian Army University Biu Campus. Each disease was caused by a specific bird species, although some of the plant diseases were caused by multiple bird species through their feeding modes, bird droppings, and nesting methods. Birds do not directly cause plant diseases; - they can only act as vectors, transmitting pathogens that cause various plant diseases. Birds can carry diseases through their droppings or by feeding on plants, which can cause soil and plant contamination. They can also spread diseases through contact with infected plants or animals.

Conclusion

The study shows that there are 44 bird species in the Nigerian Army University Biu campus which belongs to ten (10) orders and twenty six (26) families. The order Passeriformes had the highest number of species of birds. Bird species found within the campus are predominantly insectivorous and granivorous. Most of the identified birds spread both fungal and bacterial pathogens on plants. Some of the plant diseases being spread by these identified bird species include; dieback disease, Cercospora leaf spot, rice bacterial blight, bacterial blight of soybeans, powdery mildew, and Verticillium wilt diseases,

Data Availability

The data used in this study are available with the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

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References

- Abharna, K. M., and Dattu, M. A., (2015). Tour guide on Avifauna for beginners. Pp 7–15.
- Adam, L. I., Eveso, J. O., Mbaya, Y. P., Ojo, V. A., & Abdullahi, M. (2019). Avifauna checklist along Bade catchment area of River Yobe, Northeast Nigeria. In Adeyanju, O. T., Orimaye, J. O., Coker, O. M., Alarape, A. A., Ayodele, I. A., Omonona, A. O., Ojo, S. O., Ajani, F. and Ogunjinmi, A. A. (Eds.). Proceedings of the 3rd Annual Conference of the Wildlife Society of Nigeria (WISON), University of Ibadan, Ibadan, Nigeria. Pp. 256-261
- Coelho, N., Gonçalves, S., & Romano, A., (2020). Endemic plant species conservation: biotechnological approaches, *Plants* 9 (3) (2020) 345, <https://doi.org/10.3390/plants9030345>.
- De Bonilla, E. P. D., León-Cortés, J. L., & Rangel-Salazar, J. L., (2012). Diversity of bird feeding guilds in relation to habitat heterogeneity and land-use cover in a human-modified landscape in southern Mexico *J Trop Ecol.* 28:369–76.
- Derebe, Y., Derebe, B., Kassaye, M. & Gibru, A., (2023). Species diversity, relative abundance, and distribution of avifauna in different habitats within Lewi Mountain, Awi zone, Ethiopia, *Heliyon* 9 (2023) e17127 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2023.e17127>
- Desalegn, T., and Abebe, B., (2024). Diversity and Distribution of Avifauna in Northeast Addis Ababa, Central Ethiopia Hindawi, *The Scientific World Journal* 2024, Article ID 5592074, 9 pages <https://doi.org/10.1155/2024/5592074>
- Encyclopedia Britannica, (2009) retrieved July, 5th 10:55 am
- Eveso, J. O., Wakawa L. D. & Richard, R. (2022). Diversity and abundance of avifauna species in Federal University, Gashua, Northeast Nigeria. *Journal of Research in Forestry, Wildlife and Environment* Vol. 14(1), 2022
- Hailu, T., and Bezawerk, A., (2022). “The role of allele botanical garden for bird conservation in Addis Ababa, Ethiopia,” *Ethiopian Journal of Biological Sciences*, vol. 21, no. 1, pp. 527-534.
- Keesing, F., Belden, L. K., Daszak, P., Dobson, A., Harvell, C. D., Holt, R. D., Hudson, P., Jolles, A., Jones, K. E., Mitchell, C. E., Myers, S. S., Bogich, T., & Ostfeld, R. S., (2010). Impacts of biodiversity on the emergence and transmission of infectious diseases. *Nature*. Vol 4: 68, pp. 647

Muñoz-Sáez, A., Heaton, E.E., Reynolds, M., Merenlender, A.M., (2020). Agricultural adapters from the vineyard landscape impact native oak woodland birds *Agric Ecosyst Environ.* 2020; 300:106960.

National Population Commission, (2006). Retrieved June, 15th 10:05 am

Pullanikkatil, D. and Chilambo, M. (2010). **Bird Activity Book for Wildlife Clubs of Malawi**; Wildlife and Environmental Society of Malawi, Zomba. Publications: WESM Zomba branch. Pvt Bag 7 Zomba, Malawi. Pp 11–95

Shiferaw, A., & Yazezew, D. (2020). Diversity, distribution and relative abundance of avifauna at Ansas Dam and surrounding farmland site Debre Berhan Town , Ethiopia, *Avian Biol. Res.* <https://doi.org/10.1177/1758155920963200>.

Waltert, M., Bobo, K. S., Sainge, N. M., Fermon, H., Hlenberg, M. M., 2005. From forest to farmland: Effects habitat on Afrotropical forest bird diversity. *Ecol Appl.* 2005; 15: 1351–66.

Yasin, H., & Tekalign, W., (2022). A study of avifauna composition and diversity variation of along with different types of agroforestry systems in Kibet, Southern Ethiopia. *Revista Chilena de Historia Natural* 95:2 <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40693-021-00106-2>